

WORD COMBINATION OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH

Kamola Usmonova

Tashkent University of Information Technologies

named after Muhammad Al-Khwarizmi

kamolausmonova93@gmail.com

Introduction

Word combinations frequently regarded as collocations is concerned with pairing or word combinations that often happen altogether within a language. These word combinations are regarded as traditional or natural as the words constructing uniting meanings. Word combinations can comprise diverse components of speech including verbs and nouns, or adjectives and nouns, verbs and adverbs and etc. collocations or word combinations are not random pairings at simple terms of words but they are considered with their dependency mutually and the limitations that they put in each other. There are grammatical, semantic and cultural features that connect each other. For example, in the phrase “make a mistake”, “do a mistake” is not used even if the meaning is similar as “make and a mistake” is grammatically, semantically and culturally connected with each other.

Literature review

The importance of vocabulary knowledge

Language learning is a complex process including acquiring not only grammar but also, perhaps more essentially learning the vocabulary of the language. Wilkins in Thornbury (2004:13) claims that a learner can deliver something without knowing grammar but there is no possibility to say something without vocabulary. To be more precise, as words convey meaning, a speaker can deliver a message by not knowing much about the grammar structure in a foreign language by saying a word or phrases.

Vocabulary in any language is considered to be fundamental part of making use of language in practice while applying language in various contexts including listening or reading something Richards and Renandya (2002, 255). Vocabulary acquisition is a step-by-step procedure that is build gradually when making relations with other words, looking through examples as well as applying the words in connection with the context(Snow, Griffin and Burns, 2005).

Authors provide different definitions concerning the notion of vocabulary knowledge. For instance, Schmitt(2014) make a conclusion that knowledge of vocabulary is the awareness of the vocabulary components, lexical organization, as well as owning receptive and productive proficiency and smoothness. To put it another way, the notion of “knowing a word” includes not only recognizing the word but also being aware of the constructs of the word. Another definition is provided by Pullido and Hambrick (2008) concluded that vocabulary mastery is measure of the vocabulary knowledge quality of a person. By this, a learner can apply the language in practice both receptively along with productively.

One of the benefits of vocabulary comprehension is connected with writing skills. Students who have mastered satisfactory level of vocabulary generally can acquire writing skills in case of initial stages of learning (Enger,1995; Milton 2013; Park, 2012; Stehr, 2008). According to Chen et al (2015) , learners have to acquire word meaning and its usage in writing context. Milton also came to an end that students learning a foreign language should increase the vocabulary mastery with the purpose of comprehending and conveying meaning in writing.

Although there exist many ways of teaching and acquiring vocabulary knowledge, one of the best ways is the recognition and proficiency of be aware of the derivational affixes which has a direct influence on improving the quality and quantity of the vocabulary base of a learner. Derivational affixes are morphemes that make a change in the formation of the root family member resulting in the production of variants of meaning in word families. In case that a learner possesses awareness of the derivative affixes, it is more likely that they comprehend the word type as well as comprehend

the grammar in a sentence (Schmitt and Zimmerman, 2002; Mochizuki and Aizawa, 2000). Furthermore, According to Schmitt and Zimmerman (2002), learners potentially own a good opportunity to build correct language grammatically providing that they comprehend the properness of affix application. Similarly, Bauer and Nation (1993, p. 253) stated that “as a learner’s knowledge of affixation develops, the size of the word family increases”.

The notion of word combinations

The word combinations possess its specific forms and meanings grammatically. The systems of the word which is dominant creates the paradigm of the phrase. The phrase members change on the basis of the word group from which the dominant word derives from. There are a number of characteristics to consider when making classifications on the word combinations. First of all, they are characterized based on the lexical-semantic category of the dominant words. Secondly, this depends on the syntactic unit that the subordinate clause is based on. Lastly, it is dependent on the structure of the word combinations. The construction of the phrase, the way the elements is positioned based on which word class the components in the composition refers to as well as the grammatic and semantic characteristics included.

Word combinations are grouped into a number of categories on the basis of their structure as well as functions. For example, one of them is phrases which are word groups that come together as a sole unit with lacking subject-verb connection. We also can observe various functions in a sentence including noun phrases, verb phrases, prepositional as well as adjective phrases. Another type is clauses which consist of a subject and a verb which can serve as a whole sentence or a component of a sentence. In other words, they may contain independent and dependent clauses based on their meanings. For example, I will go out if it stops raining.

Third type of word combinations is constituted by including two or more individual words to establish a new word including a divergent meaning. Collocations are also another type of word combinations which often occur thanks to its implementation. They often consist of two or more words that frequently seen side by

side creating a particular phrases such as “make a mistake”, “make an effort”. Idioms are also included into word combinations including a figurative meaning in itself rather than the actual meanings of the words. They may have cultural or contextual meanings included such as “kick the bucket”, “raining cats and dogs” which may be expressed in different cultures in different ways. Prepositional phrases are also another type of word combinations including the preposition and its object which serve as the object of it. These objects give additional details about the location, time, direction and etc.

Any word can be connected grammatically and lexically to produce a compound. Vocabulary typically consists of two or more words that work together to create grammatical coherence and semantic unity. Along with the independent word that comes before it, an auxiliary word that is a part of a compound term is regarded as a component. For example, in order to dance to music with enjoyment, one needs a) dance a song and b) sing with enjoyment.

Dominant and subordinate elements can be combined to create complex words. We can comprehend this prevailing state thanks to the grammatical forms or meanings connected to that conjunction—watching a movie, black umbrella. As a result, a word’s acceptance into other forms depends on its relationship to other words and the lexico-grammatical properties of that relationship. Any grammatical or semantic "whole-syntactic construction" in speech cannot be a phrase. The differences between a word and a phrase must be listed. The meaning is clearer and the word is more general, while the sentence is more precisely defined. However, they do serve as a sentence component and remain there. In many situations, words are frequently not predicative.

In Uzbek, we can get word combination from this :

1. Haqiqatdan qo‘rqqan odam yolg‘onning panasiga berkinadi.
 - 1) Panasiga berkinadi
 - 2) Yolg‘onning panasiga
 - 3) Qo‘rqqan odam
 - 4) Haqiqatdan qo‘rqqan

2. Ertalabki kuchli shamol maktab bog‘idagi daraxtlarning mevalarini to‘kib yubordi
 - 1) Mevalarini to‘kib yubordi
 - 2) Daraxtlarning mevalarini
 - 3) Maktab bog‘idagi
 - 4) Shamol to‘kib yubordi
 - 5) Kuchli shamol
 - 6) Ertalabgi shamol
 - 7) Bog‘idagi daraxtlarni

Finding the subject and verb must come first when determining a word combination in Uzbek. Finding the word combinations is sometimes simpler once they have been underlying.

There are several word combinations in English.

The kind of Coordinated expressions

The kind of auxiliary verbs

The various predicative expressions

Conclusion

Word combinations is an important part of a language which enable the learners to make meaningful sentences and deliver their opinions fluently and effectively. Understanding of various word combinations make the non native speakers native – like and students can have a deeper comprehension of how words are connected with each other and how they can create a coherent and meaningful expressions and combinations together.

REFERENCES

3. Pulido, D. & Hambrick, D.Z. (2008). The virtuous circle: Modeling individual differences in L2 reading and vocabulary development. *Reading in a Foreign Language*, 20(2), pp.164-190;
4. Schmitt, N., & Zimmerman, C. B. (2002). Derivative Word Forms: What do learners know? *TESOL Quarterly*, 36(2), 145-171.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/3588328>;
5. Bauer, L., & Nation, I. S. P. (1993). Word families. *International Journal of Lexicography*, 6, 253–279
6. Mochizuki, Masamichi/ Aizawa, Kazumi 2000. An Affix Acquisition Order for EFL Learners: An Exploratory Study. *System*. 28/2, 291-304;
7. Cheng, J., & Matthews, J. (2018). The relationship between three measures of L2 vocabulary knowledge and L2 listening and reading. *Language Testing*, 35(1), 3-25. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265532216676851>;
8. Engber, C. (1995). The relationship of lexical proficiency to the quality of ESL compositions. *Journals of Second Language Writing*, 4, 213–238.
9. Park, B. (2012). Does the PVL T Provide an accurate measure of productive vocabulary knowledge ? *English Teaching*, 67(2), 159–183;
10. Stæhr, L. S. (2008). Vocabulary knowledge and advanced listening comprehension in English as a foreign language. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 31(4), 577-607. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263109990039>
11. Snow, C. E., Griffin, P., & Burns, M. S. (Eds.). (2005). *Knowledge to support the teaching of reading: Preparing teachers for a changing world*. Jossey-Bass/Wiley.
12. Richards, J. C., & Renandya, W. A. (2002). *Methodology in Language Teaching: An Anthology of Current Practice*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511667190>